

**Definite
CCRI**

Ref. Ares(2025)1618240 - 28/02/2025

DEFINITE-CCRI

**Dissemination, Communication
and Exploitation Plan
Final Version**

(Deliverable 6.8)

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Deliverable Number	D 6.8
Deliverable Name	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan – Final Version
Full Project Title	DEFINITE-CCRI - Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
Lead partner for deliverable	ICLEI EUROPE
Due date of deliverable	28.02.2024
Actual submission date	28.02.2024
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Author(s)	Cecilia Guinea (ICLEI EURO), Rita Cruz (CE), Dieter De Smedt (CoG).
Reviewer(s)	Nikolai Jacobi (ICLEI EURO)
Contributor(s)	All partners
WP/Task related to the deliverable	WP6/Task 6.6 DEFINITE-CCRI DisComEx Plan and tracker
Document ID	DEFINITE- CCRI_D6.8_DisseminationCommunicationExploitationPlan_FinalVersion_02.2024.pdf
Document type	Report

Executive Summary

This report serves as a final update of the communication, dissemination and exploitation strategy of the DEFINITE-CCRI project. The report aims to give professional, scientific, and public recognition to the project's achievements and outcomes.

The report outlines the targeted stakeholder groups of the project, along with the most effective communication tools and strategies to reach them. The report also considers the necessary KPIs to track the implementation of the aforementioned strategies, as well as relevant exploitation actions to maintain the project's relevance after its finalisation.

Additionally, effective internal communication is highlighted as a key element of the project's overall management.

This document serves as a final version of the D6.7 established in the Grant Agreement of the DEFINITE-CCRI project, and considers all adaptations that have needed to be integrated into the communication and dissemination activities during the implementation of the project.

DEFINITE Consortium Partners

Logo	Organisation	Type	Country
	ICLEI EURO	Small and medium-sized enterprise	Germany
	Circle Economy	Non-governmental organisation	The Netherlands
	Stad Gent	Municipality	Belgium
	Bankers without Boundaries (BWB)	Non-governmental organisation	Ireland
	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)	University	Greece

Table of Contents

<i>Executive Summary</i>	3
<i>DEFINITE Consortium Partners</i>	4
<i>List of tables</i>	7
<i>List of figures</i>	7
<i>List of abbreviations used</i>	7
<i>The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell</i>	8
<i>DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives</i>	8
<i>Introduction</i>	9
1.1. Final version.....	10
2. Internal communication	10
2.1. Gender and diversity-sensitive communication	10
2.2. Dissemination and communication strategy.....	11
Objectives.....	11
Target audiences.....	11
Key messages.....	12
Visual Identity.....	17
Templates	18
3. Communication activities	18
Project website & Web portal.....	18
Social media.....	20
Articles and press releases.....	23
E-Newsletter.....	23
Printed and digital materials.....	24
4. Dissemination activities	25
Capacity building activities	25
External events.....	26
Appraisal event and final conference.....	28
Clustering activities	29
5. Dissemination and communication KPIs	31
6. Exploitation	34
Exploitation Actions.....	34

Archive of outputs	35
Project results	35
A. <i>Technical timeline</i>	36
B. <i>Templates</i>	38

List of tables

Table 1. Target audiences	12
Table 2. Key messages	13
Table 3. DEFINITE-CCRI Partners social media handles	22
Table 4. DEFINITE-CCRI Partners social media handles	22
Table 5. List of DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletters	24
Table 6. List of training videos for the web portal	25
Table 7. List of external events where DEFINITE-CCRI was showcased	26
Table 8. DEFINITE-CCRI dissemination and communication KPIs	31
Table 9. Monitoring tools	33

List of figures

Figure 1 DEFINITE-CCRI Logo	17
Figure 2 Website structure	18

List of abbreviations used

- CCRI Circular Cities and Regions Initiative
- CIRN – Circular Investment Readiness Network
- CSA Coordination and Support Action
- EU European Union
- PDA Project Development Assistance
- WP - Work Package

The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell

Effective investment and financing opportunities for circular economy projects in Europe are still few. For securing financing, circular economy projects must meet investors' requirements for bankability and display risk-return profiles to increase investors' trust in impactful projects aimed at advancing the transition to a more circular economy in cities and regions. In order to become less risky and more appealing for investments, projects need to be developed around new and re-designed finance solutions and business models. Transaction costs need to be decreased and the private finance community needs to be engaged to address legal, administrative and market related challenges. In response to this, the DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a Deal Engine Mechanism, providing technical, financial and circular economy expertise through local Project Development Assistance (PDA) in an unprecedented and streamlined process to city and regional governments and to project developers. It aims to co-create and prove an end-to-end PDA process, aggregating risk mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the CCRI's service portfolio. This will inject the financial, technical and managerial know-how into urban circular transitions and ultimately contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Bio-economy Strategy.

DEFINITE-CCRI (*Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – CCRI*) is a Horizon Europe funded project that has started in November 2022 and is set to finish in April 2025.

DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives

The four key objectives at the foundation of the project's vision and work plan are:

- **Objective 1:** To build and operate a deal engine for the CCRI and establish it as a sustainable service offering for cities in Europe.
- **Objective 2:** To close the gap between circular economy projects in cities and regions and investors and finance partners, and to mitigate investment risks for circular economy projects.
- **Objective 3:** To increase the investment viability of innovative, high-impact circularity projects by mitigating risk and increasing their investment readiness.
- **Objective 4:** To successfully launch four investments in circular economy projects up to 20 million Euro investment volume per project in CCRI cities and regions.

Introduction

Purpose of this document

Article 17.1 of the Grant Agreement states that “the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in accordance with Annex 1 and in a strategic, coherent and effective manner”. This establishes the obligation to promote the action carried out by the partners in the scope of the project.

The main aim of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is to satisfy the above-mentioned requirement, defining a clear and comprehensive plan able to ensure a successful communication. Additionally, this updated version will assess until which point, and through which means, have such requirements been met.

The Dissemination and Communication Plan follows the guidelines “Communicating EU research and innovation - guidance for project participants” and complies with rules set by the European Commission in terms of communication and dissemination.

Structure of the document

Chapter 2 of this document outlines the management structure that has ensured coordination and effective deployment of efforts during the duration of the project while guaranteeing smooth and continuous internal communication. The chapter also presents the principles that DEFINITE-CCRI has followed to ensure gender equality and inclusivity in the project's activities.

Additionally, it offers an overview of the dissemination and communication strategy that has been followed by DEFINITE-CCRI consortium and describes the project's main objectives, key messages and target stakeholders.

Chapters 3 and 4 are focused on the communication and dissemination activities that have been realised during the project life with reference to the respective scope, timing, roles and responsibilities. These activities include the design of the project identity, the setup of communication channels, the development of printed and digital materials, the organisation of training and events and existing synergies with similar EU initiatives. Accordingly, the section also presents outcomes derived from such activities.

Chapter 5 provides the reader with detailed Information on the tools and strategies the consortium has used to monitor the performance of dissemination and communication activities and make sure they meet the relevant KPIs.

Chapter 6 is dedicated to the activities the consortium will perform to ensure a continuation of DEFINITE-CCRI's outputs after the finalisation of the project.

The annexes to this document show, in a visual way, the timeline of all communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, as well as relevant document templates.

1.1. Final version

This document serves as a final version of the dissemination, communication and exploitation strategy (D6.7) of DEFINITE-CCRI. The report constitutes an updated version of the initial plan presented in M5 of the project, and presents the relevant outputs and outcomes produced for such purpose. The document also considers all necessary adaptations that have been integrated during the implementation of the communication activities of the project.

2. Internal communication

The DEFINITE-CCRI Steering Group, composed of all Work Package Leaders, convenes bi-weekly to monitor project progress, promote information sharing among the partners, and make strategic and administrative decisions. Each Work Package Leader reports on their progress and achievements. Moreover, Work Package Leaders conduct monthly meetings to ensure that their work package activities align with the grant agreement. The consortium meets in person at least once annually.

To communicate and seek feedback between meetings, partners are encouraged to send emails to the address definite-steering@iclei.org, store and exchange documents on the online SharePoint system provided by DEFINITE-CCRI coordinator, and communicate flexibly via the Microsoft Teams group, which is organised into channels corresponding to the various work packages. Further information about DEFINITE-CCRI governance is available in the deliverable D1.1 Project Management Plan.

2.1. Gender and diversity-sensitive communication

DEFINITE-CCRI aligns with the principles of the European Union, which recognises the importance of communicating in an inclusive, accessible way, respectful of diversity. This chapter provides guidance on how to communicate in a way that is sensitive to gender and diversity.

All messages, language, and visuals within the DEFINITE-CCRI Project are designed to be inclusive and respectful of all individuals, regardless of their gender, ethnicity, religion, disability, or sexual orientation. This approach recognises that language and visuals can reinforce harmful stereotypes and discrimination, and aims to avoid such practices.

When communicating with diverse audiences, it is important to use language that is gender-neutral and avoids stereotypes. This means avoiding terms such as 'mankind' and 'he' when referring to all individuals, and using gender-neutral terms such as 'they' or 'people'. DEFINITE-CCRI project partners are encouraged to follow the [guidelines for a gender-neutral language](#) released by the European Union. Images and visuals should also be diverse and inclusive, featuring people from different backgrounds and experiences. Gender perspective and diversity have also been taken into consideration in all communication and dissemination activities, such as workshops, events and videos.

Another important aspect of gender and diversity-sensitive communication is accessibility. DEFINITE-CCRI communication materials have been designed to be accessible to all individuals. This includes using high-contrast colours and font sizes, and ensuring that any videos include subtitles.

Finally, the project complies with the respect to individuals' privacy and asks for their consent when using their images or personal information in communication materials. This applies to all individuals, but is particularly important for vulnerable groups such as children and people with disabilities.

By following the principles of gender and diversity-sensitive communication, DEFINITE-CCRI partner organisations can create a more inclusive and respectful environment, and ensure that their messages reach and resonate with diverse audiences.

2.2. Dissemination and communication strategy

The objectives of communication and dissemination are complementary. On the one hand, communication activities convey generic, non-technical and publicly available information. Their main goal is to raise awareness among non-expert audiences (i.e., the general public). On the other hand, dissemination activities deliver information on technical aspects, such as the results produced by the project, and address specific stakeholders who are likely to be interested in the replication or further development of such results.

DEFINITE-CCRI dissemination and communication strategy is aimed at addressing key stakeholders (listed in chapter 4.2) with targeted channels and activities as outlined in the following chapters.

Objectives

DEFINITE-CCRI dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities aim at:

- Promoting project activities and results among target audiences.
- Creating and operating a one-stop-shop IT infrastructure to fully digitalise and streamline the DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine process and functions.
- Implementing a capacity building program for cities and local project owners based on the experiences and expertise of DEFINITE-CCRI.
- Establishing a community of practice on circular economy project finance to create an ecosystem of external PDA providers beyond the CCRI consortium and to provide an exchange platform for project owners, cities, and investors.

Target audiences

DEFINITE-CCRI has two main objectives: to demonstrate the feasibility of high-impact circular projects and to increase maturity and trust in circular economy innovation. Therefore, the project

focuses on engaging local circular economy project owners and investors as primary target audiences. However, to ensure that the project's outcomes are adopted at various levels, additional target groups have been identified for dissemination and communication. The primary and secondary target audiences of DEFINITE-CCRI are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Target audiences

Target group	Including
1. Local Project Owners	Project owners in DEFINITE-CCRI pipeline, Circular Cities Declaration signatory cities, ICLEI Europe's member cities, public administrations and local entities, industry, and businesses and with interest/potential in circularity. Targeted sectors: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electronic & ICT • Batteries & vehicles • Packaging • Plastic • Textiles • Construction • Food, water, nutrients
2. Investors and finance partners	Green Finance Institute, European Investment Bank (EIB), European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), Cities Climate Finance Institute (CCFLA). Commercial banks and equity funds committed to circularity and sustainability (RaboBank, HSBC, ING, Lloyds, Citi, Morgan Stanley).
3. PDA service providers	CCRI, CCRI PDA projects.
4. European Policy Makers	European Commission Directorate General (e.g. DG-RTD), Commissioners, Members of the EU Parliament, the EU Mission on Climate Neutral and Smart Cities, members of EU-led or sponsored agencies.
5. General public	Citizens, NGOs and Foundations, Consumers associations.

Key messages

Key messages are concise, straightforward, and memorable statements that serve as the foundation of a project's communication and dissemination strategy. They aim to convey the project's key concepts to the targeted audience effectively. The table below outlines the key messages for the DEFINITE-CCRI Project, tailored to specific target groups and desired outcome.

Table 2. Key messages

Target group		Desired outcome	Key messages
1	Local Project Owners	Get involved in the Deal Engine Mechanism	<p>DEFINITE-CCRI offers an innovative tool to make circular economy projects bankable and secure investment deals.</p> <p>Make your project more appealing to investors, apply for DEFINITE-CCRI Deal Engine Mechanism.</p> <p>DEFINITE-CCRI will close the gap between circular economy projects and investors. Learn what investors look for, improve your business model and secure investments with DEFINITE-CCRI.</p> <p>DEFINITE-CCRI will provide support and expertise for the creation of business plans, risk profiles, feasibility studies, procurement procedures and financial solutions.</p> <p>Struggling to find funding for your circular economy project? DEFINITE- CCRI can give you technical support and guidance.</p>
		Join the Community of Practice	<p>DEFINITE-CCRI will set-up a framework for collaboration and knowledge sharing.</p> <p>A chance to grow: meet project developers, benefit from other cities' experience and share yours.</p>

Target group	Desired outcome	Key messages
	Replicate the achievements of the project by participating in DEFINITE-CCRI Capacity Building Programme	<p>DEFINITE-CCRI methodology and lessons learnt will be accessible to circular economy project developers.</p> <p>Learn from the experts and get your project funded. Enrol in DEFINITE-CCRI Capacity Building Programme.</p> <p>Get unlimited access to knowledge and tips to enhance your chances for investment.</p>
2 Investors and finance partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Being aware of the benefits of the Deal Engine Mechanism. • Understanding the scope and objectives of our work as the projects are being selected. • Offering investment criteria for potential investments. • Leveraging the network to market test financial instruments for the project portfolio. 	<p>DEFINITE-CCRI will mitigate investment risks for circular economy projects and improve their bankability.</p> <p>Investing in circular economy projects is safe and profitable with DEFINITE-CCRI. Discover new investment opportunities.</p> <p>Investing in DEFINITE-CCRI recommended projects will allow to create a more diversified portfolio while investing in climate and nature.</p>

Target group	Desired outcome	Key messages
	Getting involved: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide insights; • review project outlines; • participate as speakers in webinars. 	By participating in DEFINITE-CCRI, investors can increase the quality of investment proposals for circular economy projects. Create better investment opportunities for a circular economy with DEFINITE-CCRI Shape investment proposals the way you like them. Join DEFINITE-CCRI programme for circular economy innovation .
3 PDA service providers	Join the Community of Practice	DEFINITE-CCRI will set-up a framework for collaboration and knowledge sharing. Boost the circular transition. Enter DEFINITE-CCRI community to share your knowledge, achievements and lessons learnt with project developers from all over Europe.
4 European Policy Makers	Take up the project's recommendations (Policy Briefs) for support actions to facilitate access to investment for local and regional circular economy projects.	DEFINITE-CCRI will put European strategies and guiding frameworks into practice and will contribute to mainstreaming circularity in investments. DEFINITE-CCRI will generate useful policy insights on the implementation of the European Green Deal, the EU CEAP, the Bioeconomy Strategy and the EU Industrial Strategy. Pave the way for the circular transition. Read DEFINITE-CCRI recommendations and create better conditions for investments in circular economy. Make sure financing opportunities contribute to the creation of a more sustainable society.

Target group	Desired outcome	Key messages
	Learn about DEFINITE-CCRI case studies.	DEFINITE-CCRI will deploy local systemic circular solutions, able to attract investment and self-sustaining circular development. Discover circular economy success stories in European cities and regions.
5	General public	Learn about DEFINITE-CCRI case studies. DEFINITE-CCRI will speed-up the transition towards a more sustainable society. Reduce, reuse, recycle. Learn about the projects that will turn waste into new resources and make European cities more sustainable.
	Be aware of the benefits of circular economy.	Circular economy projects will reduce the use of resources and improve the quality of life of citizens. Save the planet: turn circular. Reducing waste and making a better use of resources is the first step for cities to be truly sustainable.

Visual Identity

The DEFINITE-CCRI Project identity was developed in the initial four months to be launched along with the project's website. It comprises visible elements, such as colour and shapes, which represent and express the symbolic meanings of the project beyond words. Alongside visual components, style guidelines are incorporated in the project's communication toolkit to ensure effective communication with the target audience. Both elements are crucial for:

- Make the project recognisable;
- Differentiate it from other initiatives;
- Assure consistency;
- Build trust and reputation.

The design of DEFINITE-CCRI identity was carried out by Circle Economy team with feedback from the whole consortium. Figure 1 shows the logo chosen by the project's partners to represent DEFINITE-CCRI.

Figure 1 DEFINITE-CCRI Logo

The logo meets several criteria, namely:

- readability and ability to stand out in different contexts (e.g., colour, black & white and negative versions);
- good performance both in small and big size;
- potential to evolve into other graphic materials;
- ability to deliver the project's topic
- uniqueness and ability to differentiate from other existing logos;
- applicability in a multi-country context;
- ability to capture attention in cluttered/confused context.

Templates

Circle Economy designed and shared with the partners the following templates to ensure consistency in the project's communication:

- A docx template to be used for the preparation of deliverables;
- A ppt template for presentations;
- A headed paper for external communications where the use of the template for deliverables is not needed;
- A flyer template to be used to promote the project across different events.

The templates, see Annex B, integrate recommended typography and colours and include the appropriate reference to the project and the acknowledgement of the funding received by the European Union.

3. Communication activities

Project website & Web portal

The project website serves as the primary platform to engage with external stakeholders and disseminate information about the project's activities and accomplishments. It is designed to attract a wide audience, with English being the language of choice to reach the largest possible audience. The website was launched in April 2023 (M5), and its structure is tailored to appeal to circular economy project owners and investors. The link to the website can be found here: <https://definite-ccri.eu/>.

Figure 2. Website structure

The "About" section of the DEFINITE-CCRI website provides key information on the project's objectives, the CCRI Initiative and sister projects. The "Invest" section is dedicated, to project owners and investors, highlighting the project's benefits and offering targeted information and links to relevant reports and insights.

The "Projects" section showcases the circular economy projects supported by the project, promoting innovative ideas in the field; while the "Network" section presents the link to the [Circular Investment Readiness Network](#), a Europe-wide community of practice co-Funded by

DEFINITE-CCR in partnership with the PDA project CircularInvest. The mission of the network is to support circular economy projects in overcoming development and funding challenges.

Additionally, the "News and Events" section features the latest updates on the project and information on events aimed at the DEFINITE-CCRI community.

Lastly, the "Resources" section includes links to documents produced by the project, including reports, presentations and insights into financing the circular economy. The DEFINITE-CCRI website is optimised for SEO to attract project owners and investors, raise awareness, and encourage the uptake of the project 's findings.

ICLEI EURO is responsible for the website's maintenance and regular update, both in terms of content and usability according to the project's needs. All partners have contributed by providing news and updates on their project-related activities. All relevant information and material produced during the project's lifetime have been uploaded on the website for free consultation and download.

The website will be maintained for at least 12 months after the end of the project.

Responsible partner	ICLEI EURO
Partners involved	CE for design, all partners for content provision.
Timing	Set up in M5 Maintenance until 12 months after the end of the project.
Related deliverable	D6.2 DEFINITE-CCRI web portal, due in M6.

Since its launch in April 2023, the website has had a total of 10,500 visits. The top five countries with the highest number of total visits to the website are the USA (2,104), the Netherlands (1,100), Germany (759), Belgium (655) and Spain (653).

A web portal is being developed as a sub-section of the DEFINITE-CCRI website. The portal is aimed at promoting the DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine, guiding interested project owners through the project development process in a step-by-step fashion. It also provides information on project finance for cities and allows circular economy project owners to submit project outlines via designated form, in line with the Data Management Plan (D1.2).

The web platform's features will be defined based on feedback from DEFINITE-CCRI partners and the first batch of circular economy projects onboarded in the first year of the project. The design principles will prioritise ease-of-use for cities and finance partners, FAIR principles for open data, and seamless data management functions in a digital one-stop-shop approach.

Many of the features devised for the web portal have been integrated into the project's main website instead. Nevertheless, a separate sub-section of the website will be created to integrate the Project Evaluation Tool (see section 6.1. Exploitation Actions, relating to Task 5.3). The portal will also include the series of short training videos developed from the project's webinars (see section 4.1. Capacity building activities). This tool and the corresponding materials will be implemented into the website before April 2025 M30.

Responsible partner	ICLEI EURO
Partners involved	CE for design, all partners for content provision.
Timing	Launch in M20.
Related deliverable	D6.2 DEFINITE-CCRI web portal, due in M6.

Social media

The social media channels for DEFINITE-CCRI, comprising a LinkedIn page and a Twitter account, were created in February 2023. On both pages, we have been publishing new content at least every two weeks. The channels aim to raise awareness about the benefits of the circular economy and the project's goals, build community with the target audience and amplify knowledge from the project's deliverables. Circle Economy is responsible for creating content and managing the channels. In addition to the channels of DEFINITE-CCRI, the social media channels will be active until Month 30 of the project (April 2025).

Frequency

A minimum of 2 posts every month. More frequent when there is a report launch or clear call to actions, such as funding opportunities.

Community building strategy

Circle Economy also created a communications kit for all partners to publish on their channels to promote the project and DEFINITE-CCRI's channels. In this way, the audience of project's partners learn about DEFINITE-CCRI and become followers. The communications kit will be updated and reshared every three months. The admin of the social media accounts will regularly monitor the comments and reply to any questions to mobilise discussions.

Tone of voice

Knowledgeable: the channels aim to show thought leadership as an expert in circular investment in Europe. For instance: refer to the reports and knowledge products of the project and cite date and evidence if applicable.

Inspiring: the channels aim to inspire the audience to think about the possibility of the transition to a circular economy in Europe. We will encourage the audience to engage with our activities. This can be done by highlighting the benefits of the solutions we suggest and the opportunities that the project provides.

Practical: be concise and avoid jargon. The channels will communicate complex ideas in simple language and focus on tangible calls to action.

Authoritative: as an EU's project, the channels aim to show an authoritative position in leading the circular economy in Europe.

Style of the visuals

Style of the visuals reflect the channel's tone of voice. See a sample of the social media visual below.

Channels milestones

The social media channels aim to mimic the programme milestones and support the project in reaching its goals.

Project launch

After launching the project, the channels will focus on raising awareness about the project and creating a social community. The content is based on the project proposal.

Report launch

We will use social media channels to amplify the findings from the project's reports. These findings will be the sources of the channel's content until there's a new development.

Funding opportunity launch

When the funding opportunity is available to the cities the channels will focus on inspiring city officials to aspire to transform their cities into a circular economy and apply for funding while building excitement among other target audiences of the possibility of circular Europe.

The main hashtags are #circulareconomy #EUGreenDeal #impactinvestment.

Table 3. DEFINITE-CCRI Partners social media handles

Title	Twitter	LinkedIn	YouTube
DEFINITE-CCRI	https://twitter.com/DEFINITE_CCRI	https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/definite-ccri/	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4beLLgLSPqFZ6ZDvtgZrFg

Table 4. DEFINITE-CCRI Partners social media handles

Partner	Twitter	LinkedIn
ICLEI EURO	https://twitter.com/ICLEI_Europe	https://www.linkedin.com/company/iclei-europe/
CE	https://twitter.com/circleconomy	https://www.linkedin.com/company/circle-economy/
BWB	https://twitter.com/bwb_bank4earth	https://www.linkedin.com/company/bankerswithoutboundaries/
CoG	https://twitter.com/Stadgent	https://www.linkedin.com/company/stad-gent/
NTUA	https://twitter.com/ntua	https://www.linkedin.com/school/national-technical-university-of-athens/

Responsible partner	Circle Economy
Partners involved	All partners for content provision.
Timing	Whole duration of the project, until M30, April 2025.
Related deliverable	-

Articles and press releases

The communication strategy to promote DEFINITE-CCRI through articles and press releases involves publishing at least 20 news and press releases on the project website and further promoting them on the main European outlets dealing with the topics of finance and circular economy. The content of the articles and press releases will focus on the project's key achievements, milestones, and major events. They will be written in an engaging and informative style, highlighting the relevance of DEFINITE-CCRI for the circular economy sector and the potential benefits for project owners and investors. The articles and press releases will be strategically timed and distributed to maximize their impact and reach a wide audience.

CE will write news and press releases based on the progress of the project and the input received by the project partners.

Responsible partner	CE
Partners involved	All partners for content provision.
Timing	Whole duration of the project, until M30, April 2025.
Related deliverable	-

E-Newsletter

Every four months the project released a periodic e-Newsletter in English to provide information on the project goals and activities and on relevant developments related to the circular economy projects supported by DEFINITE-CCRI. Each release featured an introductory text and links to the latest news and materials published on the project's website, such as public deliverables, articles, interviews, videos, and information on upcoming events.

ICLEI EURO is responsible for sending out DEFINITE-CCRI e-Newsletter to the users who registered through *SendinBlue*. After publication, the e-Newsletters have been promoted via the project's social networks and will be forwarded to the partners for further dissemination.

The following table presents an overview of the newsletters sent for the project with their corresponding open rate. A final newsletter will be released in the last two months before the project finalisation:

Table 5. List of DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletters

Month	Newsletter Title	Link	Sent to	Open rate
M11	DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletter #1	https://sh1.sendinblue.com/vtog9ktj9pfe.html?t=1739798941	38	52,63 %
M15	DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletter #2	https://sh1.sendinblue.com/vtog9ktj9pfe.html?t=1739798941	48	43,75 %
M19	DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletter #3	https://sh1.sendinblue.com/w23uxktj9pfe.html?t=1739798991	131	54,96 %
M23	DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletter #4	https://sh1.sendinblue.com/acc6ixktj9pfe.html?t=1739799022	135	59,26 %
M27	DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletter #5	https://sh1.sendinblue.com/acge89ktj9pfe.html?t=1739799046	141	60,28 %
M30	DEFINITE-CCRI Newsletter #6	--	--	--

Responsible partner	ICLEI EURO
Partners involved	CE
Timing	Expected releases: M8, M13, M19, M25, M30 This can be subject to changes depending on the project's needs.
Related deliverable	-

Printed and digital materials

Printed and digital materials have been produced throughout the duration of the project to support the promotion and dissemination of DEFINITE-CCRI's results. CE is responsible for designing such materials, which included a digital flyer, that can be printed for promotion at events and a ppt presentation to be used to introduce the project to external stakeholders. In addition, CE will produce 20 educational videos in four languages to support the dissemination of DEFINITE-CCRI's capacity building programme.

Responsible partner	CE
Partners involved	All partners, in particular CoG.
Timing	Flyer and presentation available by M4. Educational videos to be produced by M24.
Related deliverables	D6.1 Communications Toolkit, due in M4. D6.3 Capacity building materials, due in M24.

4. Dissemination activities

Capacity building activities

CoG, supported by CE and all the partners, will implement a city-led capacity building programme for CCRI cities and regions, PDA service providers, local project owners and public audiences to improve their knowledge of how to secure funding for circular projects in cities.

Instead of the 5 webinars, the consortium, in coordination with the Project Officer, has decided to produce 20 short educational videos that are created on key topics around the Deal Engine just like the originally intended webinars, but are scripted and professionally narrated, aiming for a wider audience. The videos will be more appealing visually, aiming for a much stronger impact overall.

Recordings were held in M28. Postproduction and launch will be held in M29 (D6.3). A report outlining the proceedings and results of the 20 educational videos shared, as well as a tailored plan for the wide dissemination of the 20 videos, will be provided by M30 (D6.4).

Table 6. List of training videos for the web portal

Video	Title
1.	Fast track on getting your circular project funded: The Deal Engine
2.	Circularity financing and funding landscape in Europe. An overview
3.	Is your project ready for due diligence? Financial and technical checklist
4.	Technical and impact assessment overview
5.	Explanation of the Technical and Impact assessment process and challenges
6.	Tech due diligence - service 1 – Product Market fit

7.	Tech due diligence - service 2 - Social impact
8.	Tech due diligence - service 3 – Decarbonisation
9.	Tech due diligence - service 4 – understanding your material flows
10.	Tips and tricks from project owners (technical due diligence)
11.	Financial due diligence for beginners
12.	Financial due diligence - overview
13.	Block 1: Financial Preparation – pricing strategies and market assessment
14.	Block 1: Financial modelling masterclass
15.	Block 1: Company valuation, capital raising and use of funds
16.	Block 2: Legal and regulatory preparation
17.	Block 3: Risk management
18.	Preparing a successful pitch deck
19.	Tips and tricks from project owners (financial due diligence)
20.	Reaching out to investors

Responsible partner	CoG
Partners involved	CE, All the partners.
Timing	Capacity building materials by M24 (Summarises content developed for capacity building webinars, and the delivery of 20 educational videos in 4 languages).
Related deliverable	D6.4 Report on capacity building webinars, due in M30.

External events

In order to raise awareness on the topics of the project and enrich the community of stakeholders interested in DEFINITE-CCRI, the initial communication and dissemination plan envisioned all partners to participate in at least 20 external events, national and international. This included showcasing DEFINITE-CCRI in at least one major international conference on circular economy.

Table 7 lists all the external events where DEFINITE-CCRI has been showcased

Table 7. List of external events where DEFINITE-CCRI was showcased

	Event	Date
1.	The Waste Management Europe (WME) Conference 2023	18-20 April 2023
2.	EU Green Week side event - Spin the wheel	8 June 2023
3.	European Innovation and Technology Manufacturing Network - Green and Circular Community	26 June 2023
4.	Biocircularcities unlocked – The Brussels stop	28 September 2023
5.	Circular cities: Going beyond the make-consume-dispose model	11 October 2023
6.	European Week of Regions and Cities - side event 'Accelerating circular innovation in urban landscapes	16 October 2023
7.	1st CCRI General Conference	8-9 November 2023
8.	Circular Republic Festival 2023	15-18 November 2023
9.	Circular Cities: Progressing on Climate and Biodiversity	15 February 2024
10.	Circular Black Forest - Auftaktveranstaltung Freiburg	22 February 2024
11.	Flanders Technology and Innovation Ghent	20-21 March 2024
12.	The Waste Management Europe (WME) Conference 2024	9-10 April 2024
13.	World Circular Economy Forum 2024	15-18 April 2024
14.	Tech Tour Circular 2024 - Ghent	23-24 April 2024
15.	5th Symposium on Circular Economy and Sustainability & 26th INFER Annual Conference	18-20 June 2024
16.	The Fifteenth International Conference on Information, Intelligence, Systems and Applications (IISA 2024)	17-20 July 2024
17.	10th European Conference on Sustainable Cities and Towns	1-3 October 2024
18.	Developers of Circular Solutions (DECISO) 1st Annual Conference	9 October 2024
19.	Barcelona Circular Innovation Summit	7 November 2024
20.	DEFINITE-CCRI stakeholder workshop	12-14 November 2024

Responsible partner	ICLEI EURO, CE
Partners involved	All the partners
Timing	Whole duration of the project.
Related deliverable	-

Appraisal event and final conference

This task is a crucial part of the project that aims to identify and review the circular economy projects supported by the DEFINITE-CCRI Project, providing a thorough due diligence assessment to potential investors and technical partners. The appraisal process involved a comprehensive review of projects by potential investors and technical partners. The process evaluated the readiness of projects for financing, resulting in either a 'stamp of approval' for adequately qualified projects or detailed recommendations for improvement for those projects requiring further refinement. The process consisted of three main phases: 1) Project Preparation; 2) Appraisal Event Preparation, 3) Post-Appraisal Proceedings.

After the assessment of several options, the DEFINITE-CCRI consortium decided to split the appraisal event into two separate events, one in Barcelona (November 7th 2024) and the other in Brussels (November 13th 2024). The reasoning behind this decision was driven by several factors, specified in *D5.2. Report on Project Appraisal Proceedings*, an overview of the agenda and the key takeaways from the event can also be found in D5.2.

The Barcelona Appraisal Event (named "[The Barcelona Circular Innovation Summit](#)") was organised with the objective of garnering attention and ensuring the presence of impact investors joining the Norrsken Impact Week in Barcelona. It was centered around the presentation of the Circular Library Network and its achievements after the first round of due diligence. Accordingly, the Brussels Appraisal Event ("[3rd Coordination and Support Workshop](#)") allowed for a strategic proximity with the main locations and investors, helped identify synergies with other CCRI PDA projects, and showcased the work to EU Commission representatives and other partnering organisations.

Feedback from both events was thoroughly reviewed and integrated afterwards.

Regarding the final conference of the DEFINITE-CCRI project, it must be noted that the program of is currently under preparation. The event will be run in a "talk-show format", including a panel of key stakeholders from all three core groups, i.e. projects/solution providers, investors, policy makers + one from an incubator/multiplier etc. The event aims to gather participants from the European policy sphere as well as start-ups/incubators and investors who are engaged in developing or financing circular solutions or are setting the relevant framework conditions at European level. The objectives of the final conference are:

- Present key results of the DEFINITE-CCRI project to relevant stakeholders;
- Discuss relevant policy recommendations on circular economy Project Development Assistance (PDA) with European policy stakeholders
- Engage, discuss and disseminate with local start-ups and projects as well as with local government officials and investors.

The event will have a hybrid format. It will be held in Sint Pietersabdij, Ghent, Belgium on Wednesday 9th April from 14.30-20h.

Responsible partner	BWB, ICLEI EURO
Partners involved	All the partners
Timing	M24
Related deliverable	D5.1 Report on Project Appraisal Event and Final Conference, due in M24.

Clustering activities

Throughout the project, ICLEI will ensure a close collaboration with the wider CCRI community by maintaining regular contact with the CCRI-CSO. In February 2023 a meeting with other PDA projects took place to identify potential areas of cooperation, avoid duplication, and facilitate the exchange of best practices, knowledge, and data.

The consortium partners have actively participated in the biannual general CCRI conference and regular CCRI workshops on the following topics:

- Circular Construction and Buildings;
- Bioeconomy;
- Circular Resource Management;
- Industrial symbiosis and circular economy in industries.

The CCRI-CSO has been informed of all the events organised by DEFINITE-CCRI and has been invited to participate.

To share the lessons learned from the DEFINITE-CCRI project with the CCRI community and beyond, two policy briefs are being produced by ICLEI EURO, one of which has been submitted already in M12. A second, final policy brief will be developed by M32 (June 2025). These briefs, target European policymakers, containing positions and recommendations on relevant on-going EU policy initiatives such as the Competitiveness Fund and highlight recommendations on how to strengthen circular project financing for cities and regions – both public and private. The production of these briefs will be coordinated and shared within the CCRI-CSO framework to ensure wider dissemination.

Responsible partner	ICLEI EURO
Partners involved	All partners

Timing	Whole duration of the project.
Related deliverables	D6.9 Policy Brief 1, due in M12. D6.10 Policy Brief 2, due in M30.

5. Dissemination and communication KPIs

The following table summarises the impact of the actions illustrated in this report.

Table 8. DEFINITE-CCRI dissemination and communication KPIs

Tool/Action	Partner	Releases	KPIs (Feb 2025)	Goals	Timing
Communications Toolkit	CE	1	1	Release of a Communication Toolkit including guidelines, templates and promotional materials.	M4
Project website	ICLEI EURO	2	8,106 (visitors)	Launch of a project website, at least 5,000 visitors. Launch of a web platform for the Deal Engine Mechanism.	M6 M20
Outreach to cities	ALL	-	-		M12
Social media	CE		0.80%	0,5% engagement rate on selected platforms.	Throughout the project duration
Articles and press releases	CE	20	25	Publication of at least 20 news and press releases on DEFINITE-CCRI website + promotion in thematic European magazines and platforms.	Throughout the project duration
e-Newsletter	ICLEI EURO	5	5*	500 subscribers by M30	M7, M12, M19, M24, M29

External events	ALL	20	19 (events) +2K (people)	>2,000 people reached	By M30
Final Conference	ICLEI EURO	1		50 participants	M24
Community of practice	CoG	5	4 (CoP) 449 (partic.)	5 webinars 300 unique participants	By M30
Training materials	CE	20		20 educational videos At least 2,000 views in total	M24 By M30
Policy Briefs	ICLEI EURO	2	1	Release of 2 policy briefs	M12 M30
Clustering activities	ICLEI EURO	-		Participation in CCRI working groups workshops (3 workshops a year per each theme) and in the biannual conference.	Throughout the project duration

*An additional and final Newsletter will be launched in April 2025.

To ensure the effectiveness of communication and dissemination activities, a comprehensive monitoring process will be implemented to assess their outreach and impact. This process will enable the project team to regularly update and refine their communication and dissemination strategy based on the findings.

To gather information on the outreach of the project's content, ICLEI EURO and CE are using a combination of automated and manual tools. The tools and methods for collecting data on DEFINITE-CCRI communication and dissemination activities are summarised in the table below.

While online activities can be monitored through automated tools, offline activities such as participating in events and publishing articles in printed magazines will require the project partners to collect relevant and complete data. This will be facilitated through a shared online form under the supervision of ICLEI EURO.

Table 9. Monitoring tools

Activity	Measurement tool	Main parameters
Website	Matomo	Pageviews, visitors, most viewed pages, average session duration
News and press releases dissemination	Statistics provided by online platforms, online search	Pageviews/visitors, total outreach, take-ups
Social Media	Twitter Analytics, LinkedIn statistics	Number of posts, viewers, external outreach
Online Videos	YouTube Stats	Number of views
Deliverables and communication materials uploaded on DEFINITE-CCRI website	Matomo	Number of downloads

6. Exploitation

Exploitation Actions

All project partners will directly exploit project results in their respective tasks and deliverables, beyond the project by including gained experience and know-how in current and future work they are involved in. This will help to guarantee that in the future more cities and regions will be helped beyond DEFINITE-CCRI.

To ensure a continuation of DEFINITE-CCRI's outputs, European cities and regions will have access to the knowledge and knowhow created via the following channels mentioned throughout the report:

- DEFINITE-CCRI web portal in the Project's website (with open repository under the rules of the FAIR principles);
- Social Media channels (as mentioned above, on Chapter 5, Know-how, processes, frameworks, advisory content and experiences by consortium partners will be shared publicly via the channels defined in WP6 and remain accessible to all partners, cities, the wider CCRI and respective stakeholders.
- Ganbatte Cities Tool (this is a digital platform provided by Circle Economy Foundation. ICLEI and CE will explore the integration of learnings from DEFINITE-CCRI into the tool).
- Project Evaluation Tool (T5.3.) As part of Task 5.3., DEFINITE-CCRI will develop a Project Evaluation Tool (M18-M24) that will become part of its permanent service officer to cities beyond the project lifetime.
- Capacity Building materials (T6.4.) will be uploaded to the DEFINITE-CCRI YouTube channel, and embedded in existing website and socials;
- A self-sustaining support program for cities (T6.6.), ensuring replication and ongoing service provision. All of this will be publicly available.

While all processes created by the consortium will remain public, the developed branding of DEFINITE-CCRI and the Deal Engine will remain the project legacy in name. All access to data, intellectual property of any kind of information on local projects shared by cities or local project owners for the purpose of receiving PDA via DEFINITE-CCRI will remain with the respective owners unless explicitly agreed otherwise. Data and information to be shared publicly such as project descriptions or those necessary to be shared with investors will be clearly identified as such during the submission of project outlines to DEFINITE-CCRI (WP2).

Overall, the project DEFINITE-CCRI deal engine will publicly prove the viability of innovative finance for closed-loop material value chains as profitable investment opportunities and provide a practical application of the EU Taxonomy. The project will be a permanent platform for Europe, to

provide an ongoing, crucial service assisting local and regional circular economy project developers in developing bankable projects for investment.

Archive of outputs

All produced outputs regarding the project are stored on the DEFINITE-CCRI website.

Project results

The creation of a Project Spin-off Plan (Deliverable 6.6.), under preparation at the moment of writing, will guarantee that the project results will have continuation after the completion of all tasks (M30). The spin-off will form a concrete continuation of the partnership dedicated to the self-sustaining (potentially commercial) future exploitation and continuous improvement of project-generated processes, partnerships and know-how.

In addition, at the end of the project, an extensive communication kit about the project's results and knowledge products will be created and shared with the project partners and wider network to ensure that the results of the project will continue to be amplified. Circle Economy will ensure to mention the project on its social media channels even after the project ends.

A. Technical timeline

Task	Description	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15
6.1	Communications Toolkit															
6.1	Social media															
6.1	Articles and press releases															
6.1	e-Newsletter															
6.2	Project website															
6.2	Web portal															
6.3	Capacity Building Programme															
6.4	Community of Practice															
5.1	Appraisal event															
5.2	Final Conference															
6.5	Project spin-off plan															
6.6	DisComEx Plan and tracker															
6.7	Clustering & policy briefs															

Task	Description	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
6.1	Communications Toolkit															
6.1	Social media															
6.1	Articles and press releases															
6.1	e-Newsletter															
6.2	Project website															
6.2	Web portal															
6.3	Capacity Building Programme															
6.4	Community of Practice															
5.1	Appraisal event															
5.2	Final Conference															
6.5	Project spin-off plan															
6.6	DisComEx Plan and tracker															
6.7	Clustering & policy briefs															

B. Templates

Word template for deliverables

DEFINITE-CCRI

Communication Toolkit

(Deliverable 6.1)

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or EEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Definite-CCRI
Horizon 2022 - Communication Toolkit

Lead partner for deliverable	ICLEI EUROPE
Document type	Report
Due date of deliverable	28.02.2023
Actual submission date	20.01.2023
Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Author(s)	Alexandru Grigoras (CE), Rita Cruz (CE), Kristin Strandberg (CE)
Reviewer(s)	Roman Mendle (ICLEI), Asen Charliyaki (BwB), Alexandros Nikas (NTUA), Heidi Tenzy (CoG).
Contributor(s)	All partners

Cite as: K. Strandberg, R. Cruz, A. Grigoras. (2023). DEFINITE-CCRI PDA-EU. Communication Toolkit (Deliverable 6.1).

D.6.1 Communication toolkit

2 / 11

Definite-CCRI
Horizon 2022 - Communication Toolkit

Executive Summary

The Communication Toolkit is the first deliverable of Work Package 6, within the umbrella of the Definite-CCRI project. This document is a word template created for the Definite Consortium to use throughout the duration of the project to produce reports or any other document relevant to the project.

Communication Toolkit Objectives

The key objectives of the Communication Toolkit are:

- Objective 1: Provide the Consortium with a template example that can later be used throughout the project.
- Objective 2: Guarantee that we have a standardisation of documents harmonising our outputs externally.

D.6.1 Communication toolkit

3 / 11

DEFINITE-CCRI
Horizon 2022 - Communication Toolkit

The DEFINITE-CCRI Project in a Nutshell

Effective investment and financing opportunities for circular economy projects in Europe are still few. For securing financing, circular economy projects must meet investors' requirements for bankability and display risk-return profiles to increase investors' trust in impactful projects aimed at advancing the transition to a more circular economy in cities and regions. In order to become less risky and more appealing for investments, projects need to be developed around new and re-designed finance solutions and business models. Transaction costs need to be decreased and the private finance community needs to be engaged to address legal, administrative and market related challenges. In response to this, the DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a Deal Engine Mechanism, providing technical, financial and circular economy expertise through local Project Development Assistance (PDA) in an unprecedented and streamlined process to city and regional governments and to project developers. It aims to co-create and pilot an end-to-end PDA process, aggregating risk mitigation, EU Taxonomy compliance, circularity criteria and technical and financial engineering in a single project development service for the CCRI's service portfolio. This will inject the financial, technical and managerial know-how into urban circular transitions and ultimately contribute to lower virgin non-renewable material use, lower GHG emissions and more just and inclusive circular employment in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan and the Bio-economy Strategy.

DEFINITE-CCRI (Deal Engine, with finance, investment and technical expertise for the European Commission's Circular Cities and Regions initiative - CCRI) is a Horizon Europe funded project that has started in November 2022.

DEFINITE-CCRI Objectives

The four key objectives at the foundation of the project's vision and work plan are:

- Objective 1: To build and operate a deal engine for the CCRI and establish it as a sustainable service offering for cities in Europe.
- Objective 2: To close the gap between circular economy projects in cities and regions and investors and finance partners, and to mitigate investment risks for circular economy projects.
- Objective 3: To increase the investment viability of innovative, high-impact circularity projects by mitigating risk and increasing their investment readiness.
- Objective 4: To successfully launch four investments in circular economy projects up to 20 million Euro investment volume per project in CCRI cities and regions.

D.6.1 Communication toolkit

7 / 8

Project Flyer

Get involved...

- 1 Learn what investors look for, improve your business model and secure investment!
- 2 Struggling to find funding for your circular economy project? DEFINITE-CCRI can give you technical support and guidance.

contact@definite-ccri.eu

www.definite-ccri.eu

DEFINITE-CCRI

The DEFINITE-CCRI project establishes a deal engine, providing technical, financial and circular economy expertise through local project development assistance in an unprecedented and streamlined process to cities, regions and project developers.

The Deal Engine Mechanism

DEFINITE-CCRI offers an innovative tool to make circular economy projects bankable and secure investment deals. Through the Deal Engine - Mechanism, DEFINITE-CCRI will close the gap between circular economy projects and investors. The programme will provide support and expertise for the creation of business plans, risk profiles, feasibility studies, procurement procedures and financial solutions.

**Definite
CCRI**

